

Implementation of Computational Algorithms using Parallel Programming

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ABSTRACT

Parallel computing is a type of computation in which many processing are performed concurrently often by dividing large problems into smaller ones that execute independently of each other. There are several different types of parallel computing. The first one is the shared memory architecture which harnesses the power of multiple processors and multiple cores on a single machine and uses threads of programs and shared memory to exchange data. The second type of parallel computing is the distributed architecture which harnesses the power of multiple machines in a networked environment and uses message passing to communicate processes actions to one another. This paper implements several computational algorithms using parallel programming techniques namely distributed message passing. The algorithms are Mandelbrot set, Bucket Sort, Monte Carlo, Grayscale Image Transformation, Array Summation, and Insertion Sort algorithms. All these algorithms are to be implemented using C#.NET and tested in a parallel environment using the MPI.NET SDK and the DeinoMPI API. Experiments conducted showed that the proposed parallel algorithms have faster execution time than their sequential counterparts. As future work, the proposed algorithms are to be redesigned to operate on shared memory multi-processor and multi-core architectures.

KEYWORDS: Parallel Computing, Distributed Algorithms, Message Passing

I. MANDELBROT SET ALGORITHM

The Mandelbrot set is a set of points in the complex plane, the boundary of which forms a fractal. Mathematically, the Mandelbrot set can be defined as the set of complex c -values for which the orbit of 0 under iteration of the complex quadratic polynomial $x_{n+1}=x_n^2 + c$ remains bounded [1].

We have designed our parallel algorithm based on generic static assignment approach where each node in a cluster is responsible for a pre-defined set of points. The master will identify the number of available slaves and assign a number of points or pixels to each active slave. Each slave then will apply the Mandelbrot algorithm to decide whether or not a particular pixel belongs to the set. Ultimately results will be collected by the master node which will display graphically the set of pixels. The execution time of the parallel algorithm is recorded and reported by the master node.

A. Implementation & Experiments

The proposed algorithm is implemented under MS Visual C# 2015 and the MS .NET Framework 3.5 [2]. The message passing interface used is the proprietary MPI.NET SDK [3]. As a testing platform, a single computer has been used with Intel Core Dual Core 1.66Ghz CPU and 512MB of DDR2 RAM. Table 1 delineates the results obtained

Table 1: Mandelbrot Testing Results

Number of iterations	20000
Sequential execution time	18s 578ms
Parallel execution time	8s 78ms
Speedup factor	$t_s / t_p = 18578/8078 = 2.3$

Figure 1 shows the execution of the Mandelbrot set program over 2 cores. The master drew the pixels in purple while the slave drew it in red.

Figure 1: Mandelbrot Program

B. Source Code

```

private void Start()
{
    int width = 640, height = 480;
    double complexReal, complexImag;
    double MIN_REAL = -2; // FIXED
    double MAX_REAL = 2; // FIXED
    double MIN_IMAG = -2; // FIXED
    double MAX_IMAG = 2; // FIXED

    Bitmap bitmap1 = new Bitmap(width, height);
    DateTime t1 = DateTime.Now; // Start time

    string[] args = null;
    using (new MPI.Environment(ref args))
    {
        Communicator comm = Communicator.world;

        int region = height/num_proc ;
        if (comm.Rank == 0) // MASTER
        {
            for (int i=0, z=1 ; z<num_proc; i=i+region+1 , z++)
            {
                comm.Send( i , z, 0); // send the height_From to
                RANK z with TAG 0
                comm.Send( i+region , z, 1); // send the
                height_To to RANK z with TAG 1
            }
            for (int x = 0; x < width; x++) // x = x co-ordinate
            of pixel
            {
                for (int y = 0; y < height / 2; y++) // y = y co-
                ordinate of pixel
                {
                    complexReal = MIN_REAL + x * (MAX_REAL -
                    MIN_REAL) / width;
                    complexImag = MIN_IMAG + y * (MAX_IMAG -
                    MIN_IMAG) / height;

                    int iteration = cal_pixel(complexReal,
                    complexImag);
                    if (iteration == max_iteration)
                        bitmap1.SetPixel(x, y, Color.BlueViolet);
                    else bitmap1.SetPixel(x, y, Color.Black);
                }
            }

            Bitmap bitmap2 = comm.Receive<Bitmap>(1, 1);
            DateTime t2 = DateTime.Now; // Stop time
            TimeSpan duration = t2 - t1;
            timeLabel.Text = "Time: " + duration.Seconds +
            "s " +
            duration.Milliseconds + "ms";

            // Display the MandelBrot Set
            pictureBox1.BackgroundImage =
            (Image)bitmap1;
            pictureBox2.BackgroundImage =
            (Image)bitmap2;
        }
        else // ANY SLAVE
        {
            int height_From = comm.Receive<int>(0, 0);
            int height_To = comm.Receive<int>(0, 1);

            Bitmap bitmap2 = new Bitmap(width, height);

            for (int x = 0; x < width; x++) // x = x co-ordinate
            of pixel
            {
                for (int y = height_From; y < height_To; y++)
                {
                    complexReal = MIN_REAL + x * (MAX_REAL -
                    MIN_REAL) / width;
                    complexImag = MIN_IMAG + y * (MAX_IMAG -
                    MIN_IMAG) / height;

                    int iteration = cal_pixel(complexReal,
                    complexImag);

                    if (iteration == max_iteration)
                        bitmap2.SetPixel(x, y, Color.Red);
                    else bitmap2.SetPixel(x, y, Color.Black);
                }
            }

            comm.Send(bitmap2, 0, 1); // send the bitmap to
            RANK 0 with TAG 1
        }
    }
}

private int cal_pixel(double complexReal, double
complexImag)
{
    double lengthsq, temp;
    double real = 0, imag = 0; // Always Initial Values

    int iteration = 0;
    do
    {
        temp = (real * real) - (imag * imag) + complexReal;
        imag = 2 * real * imag + complexImag; // Fixed
        Formula
        real = temp;
        lengthsq = real * real + imag * imag; // Fixed
        Formula
        iteration++;
    }
    while ((lengthsq < 4.0) && (iteration <
    max_iteration));
    return iteration;
}

```

II. BUCKET SORT ALGORITHM

Bucket sort, or bin sort, is a sorting algorithm that works by partitioning an array into a number of buckets. Each bucket is then sorted individually, either using a different sorting algorithm, or by recursively applying the bucket sorting algorithm [4]. The proposed parallel algorithm is primary based on a binary approach. The MSB (Most Significant Bit) of each randomly generated number will indicate the allocation bucket. Upon end, each bucket is sorted apart using the Bubble sort algorithm. As for the parallel design, each slave node will be responsible for one bucket to sort. In case of having the number of slaves less than the number of buckets, each slave will then handle more than one bucket at the same time. Eventually, the master node displays the results as a single sorted list of digits. The execution time of the proposed parallel algorithm is recorded and reported by the master node.

A. Implementation & Experiments

The proposed algorithm is implemented under MS Visual C# 2015 and the MS .NET Framework 3.5. The message passing interface used is the proprietary MPI.NET SDK. As a testing platform, a single computer has been used with Intel Core Dual Core 1.66Ghz CPU and 512MB of DDR2 RAM. Table 2 delineates the results obtained

Table 2: Bucket Sort Testing Results

Number of iterations	30000
Sequential execution time	10s 437ms
Parallel execution time	3s 875ms
Speedup factor	$t_s / t_p = 10437 / 3875 = 2.7$

B. Source Code

```
private void Start()
{
    // Generate Random Numbers to SORT
    Random rand = new Random();
    int[] list = new int[30000];
    for (int i = 0; i < list.Length; i++)
        list[i] = rand.Next(0, 255);
    BucketSort(list);
}

public void BucketSort(int[] list)
{
    ArrayList[] buckets = new ArrayList[8]; // 8 buckets -->
    requires 3-bits
    for (int i = 0; i < buckets.Length; i++)
    {
        buckets[i] = new ArrayList(); // create object
        buckets
    }
    DateTime t1 = DateTime.Now; // Start Time
    for (int i = 0; i < list.Length; i++)
    {
        string number = ConvertToBinary(list[i]);
        string MSB = number.Substring(0, 3); // taking the
        3 MSBs
        int integer = ConvertToDecimal(MSB);
        buckets[integer].Add(list[i]); // add number to the
        corresponding bucket
    }
    // Update GUI Labels with numbers
    for (int i = 0; i < buckets[6].Count - 1; i++)
        label7.Text = label7.Text + buckets[6][i].ToString()
        + ", ";
    for (int i = 0; i < buckets[7].Count - 1; i++)
        label8.Text = label8.Text + buckets[7][i].ToString()
        + ", ";
    // At this point all BUCKETS are filled with numbers
    string[] args = null;
    using (new MPI.Environment(ref args))
```

```
{
    Communicator comm = Communicator.world;
    if (comm.Rank == 0) // MASTER
    {
        this.Text = "MASTER"; // Set TitleBar
        string sortedList = "";

        // send the the first 4 buckets to the slave
        for (int i = 0; i < 4; i++)
            comm.Send(buckets[i], 1, i); // send to RANK 1
            with TAG i+1

        // SORT bucket #5 to bucket #8
        for (int i = 4; i < buckets.Length; i++)
            sortedList = sortedList +
            BubbleSort(buckets[i]);

        outputTextbox.Text = comm.Receive<string>(1,
        5) + sortedList;

        DateTime t2 = DateTime.Now; // Stop Time
        TimeSpan duration = t2 - t1;
        timeLabel.Text = "Time: " + duration.Seconds +
        "s " +
            duration.Milliseconds + "ms";
    }
    else // SLAVE
    {
        this.Text = "SLAVE"; // Set TitleBar
        string sortedList = "";
        ArrayList[] buckets_SLAVE = new ArrayList[4];
        for (int i = 0; i < buckets_SLAVE.Length; i++)
        {
            buckets_SLAVE[i] =
            comm.Receive<ArrayList>(0, i);
            sortedList = sortedList +
            BubbleSort(buckets_SLAVE[i]);
        }
        comm.Send(sortedList, 0, 5);
    }
} // end of USING statement

private string BubbleSort(ArrayList bucket)
{
    // Bubble Sort
    // converting ArrayList object to a regular int array
    int[] array = new int[bucket.Count];
    for (int i = 0; i < bucket.Count; i++)
        array[i] = Convert.ToInt32(bucket[i].ToString());

    int temp;
    for (int i = 0; i < array.Length; i++)
    {
        for (int j = 0; j < array.Length; j++)
        {
            if (array[i] < array[j])
            {
                temp = array[i];
                array[i] = array[j];
                array[j] = temp;
            }
        }
    }
}
```

```
// Displaying the sorted numbers
string sortedList = "";
for (int i = 0; i < array.Length; i++)
    sortedList = sortedList + array[i] + ", ";

return sortedList;
}
```

III. MONTE CARLO ALGORITHM

The Monte Carlo is a computational algorithm that relies on repeated random sampling to compute its results [5]. Monte Carlo methods are often used when simulating physical and mathematical systems. Because of their reliance on repeated computation and random or pseudo-random numbers, Monte Carlo methods are most suited to calculation by a computer. In this problem, we are using the Monte Carlo method to estimate to value of Pi.

The proposed algorithm is mainly a parallel implementation of the renowned Monte Carlo problem. Since there are a maximum number of iterations after which the algorithm should stop, it is natural to partition the number of iterations per singular nodes. In this sense, each node including the master node will be responsible for a specific number of iterations less than the total maximum of iterations. Finally, the master will collect back the results and display the final value of Pi.

A. Implementation & Experiments

The proposed algorithm is implemented under MS Visual C# 2015 and the MS .NET Framework 3.5. The message passing interface used is the proprietary MPI.NET SDK. As a testing platform, a single computer has been used with Intel Core Dual Core 1.66Ghz CPU and 512MB of DDR2 RAM. Table 3 delineates the results obtained.

Table 3: Bucket Sort Testing Results

Number of iterations	50000000
Sequential execution time	7s 359ms
Parallel execution time	3s 890ms
Speedup factor	$t_s / t_p = 7359/3890 = 1.9$

B. Source Code

```
private void Start()
{
    Random rand = new Random();

    string[] args = null;
    using (new MPI.Environment(ref args))
    {
        Communicator comm = Communicator.world;
        if (comm.Rank == 0) // MASTER
        {
            this.Text = "MASTER";
            DateTime t1 = DateTime.Now; // Start Time

            comm.Send(max_iterations, 1, 0); // To RANK 1 with TAG 0

            double x, y, z, PI;
            int count = 0;
```

```
for (int i = 0; i < max_iterations/2; i++)
{
    x = (double)rand.Next(32767) / 32767;
    y = (double)rand.Next(32767) / 32767;
    z = x * x + y * y;
    if (z <= 1) count++;
}

int countREC = comm.Receive<int>(1, 1); // From RANK 1 with TAG 1

PI = (double)(count+countREC) / max_iterations * 4;

PILabel.Text = "Pi = " + PI;

DateTime t2 = DateTime.Now; // Stop Time
TimeSpan duration = t2 - t1;
timeLabel.Text = "Time: " + duration.Seconds + "s " +
    duration.Milliseconds + "ms"
;
}
else // SLAVE
{
    this.Text = "SLAVE";

    int max_iterationsREC = comm.Receive<int>(0, 0);
    double x, y, z, PI;
    int count = 0;
    for (int i = max_iterationsREC / 2; i <
        max_iterationsREC; i++)
    {
        x = (double)rand.Next(32767) / 32767;
        y = (double)rand.Next(32767) / 32767;
        z = x * x + y * y;
        if (z <= 1) count++;
    }
    comm.Send(count, 0, 1); // To RANK 0 with TAG 1
} // end of using STATEMENT
}
```

IV. GRAYSCALE IMAGE TRANSFORMATION

Digital Image Transformations are a fundamental part of computer graphics. Transformations are used to scale objects, to shape objects, and to position objects [6]. In this problem, we are converting a 24-bit colored image into an 8-bit grayscale image.

The proposed parallel algorithm will embarrassingly assign different regions of the picture to each of the available and active nodes. Each node will work on its dedicated part then the transformed pixels are sent back to the master node. The master node eventually displays the complete transformed image.

A. Implementation

The proposed algorithm is implemented under MS Visual C# 2015 and the MS .NET Framework 3.5. The message passing interface used is the proprietary MPI.NET SDK. As a testing platform, a single computer has been used with Intel Core Dual Core 1.66Ghz CPU and 512MB of DDR2 RAM. Table 4 delineates the results obtained

Table 4: Image Transformation Testing Results

Image size	698x475 pixels
Sequential execution time	0s 953ms
Parallel execution time	0s 718ms
Speedup factor	$t_s / t_p = 953/718 = 1.3$

Figure 2 depicts two transformed regions of the same image. The master nodes handled the left part; while, the slave nodes handled the right part.

Figure 2: Grayscale Image Transformation Program

B. Source Code

```
private void Start()
{
    DateTime t1 = DateTime.Now; // Start time
    string[] args = null;
    using (new MPI.Environment(ref args))
    {
        Communicator comm = Communicator.world;
        if (comm.Rank == 0) // MASTER
        {
            Bitmap bitmap1 = new Bitmap(pictureBox1.Image,
                pictureBox1.Width, pictureBox1.Height);
            comm.Send(pictureBox1.Width / 2, 1, 0); // send to
            RANK 1 with TAG 0
            for (int y = 0; y < bitmap1.Height; y++)
            {
                for (int x = 0; x < bitmap1.Width / 2; x++)
                {
                    Color c = bitmap1.GetPixel(x, y);
                    //Formula: grayPixel = 0.3*RED + 0.59*GREEN
                    + 0.11*BLUE
                    int grayPixel = (int)(c.R * 0.3 + c.G * 0.59 + c.B *
                        0.11);
                    bitmap1.SetPixel(x, y,
                        Color.FromArgb(grayPixel, grayPixel,
                            grayPixel));
                }
            }
            pictureBox1.Image = (Image)bitmap1;
            DateTime t2 = DateTime.Now; // Stop time
            TimeSpan duration = t2 - t1;
            timeLabel.Text = "Time: " + duration.Seconds + "s "
                +
                duration.Milliseconds + "ms";
        }
        else // SLAVE
        {
            int width_Rec = comm.Receive<int>(0, 0);
            Bitmap bitmap2 = new Bitmap(pictureBox1.Image,
                pictureBox1.Width, pictureBox1.Height);
            for (int y = 0; y < bitmap2.Height; y++)
```

```
{
    for (int x = width_Rec; x < bitmap2.Width; x++)
    {
        Color c = bitmap2.GetPixel(x, y);
        //Formula: grayPixel = 0.3*RED +
        0.59*GREEN + 0.11*BLUE
        int grayPixel = (int)(c.R * 0.3 + c.G * 0.59 + c.B
            * 0.11);
        bitmap2.SetPixel(x, y,
            Color.FromArgb(grayPixel, grayPixel,
                grayPixel));
    }
}
pictureBox1.Image = (Image)bitmap2;
}
```

V. ARRAY SUMMATION

The problem of array summation is to add together 5,000,000 numbers contained in a one-dimensional array [7]. The master node would broadcast the content of the initial array to all the available slaves. Each slave would then add together each two contiguous integers and send the partial sum back to the master node. After long run, the master node adds all those accumulated partial sums to get a final result.

A. Implementation

The proposed algorithm is implemented under MS Visual C++ 6.0 [8]. The message passing interface used is the proprietary MPI 2.0 standard DeinoMPI [9]. As a testing platform, two computers connected by a 100Mbps Ethernet have been used with Intel Core Dual Core 1.66Ghz CPU and 512MB of DDR2 RAM. Table 5 delineates the results obtained

Table 5: Pixel Summation Testing Results

Number to add	5000000
Sequential execution time	1s 798ms
Parallel execution time	0s 323ms
Speedup factor	$t_s / t_p = 1798/323 = 5.56$

B. Source Code

```
void main(int argc, char* argv[])
{
    int my_rank; // Holds my rank: 0 for master and other
    numbers for slaves
    int num_proc; // Holds the number of processors
    available
    MPI_Status status;
    MPI_Init(&argc, &argv);
    MPI_Comm_rank(MPI_COMM_WORLD, &my_rank);
    MPI_Comm_size(MPI_COMM_WORLD, &num_proc);
    int partition_size = 5000000/num_proc ; // Partition
    Numbers among processes
    if (my_rank == 0) // MASTER
    {
        int data[5000000] = ;
```

```

for(int i=0 ; i<50000 ; i++)
    data[i] = i ;

clock_t t1 = clock();

MPI_Bcast(data , 50000 , MPI_INT , 0 ,
MPI_COMM_WORLD);

int sum=0, partial_sum=0 , sumREC=0;

for(int k=0 ; k<partition_size ; k++)
    partial_sum = partial_sum + data[k] ;

for(int i=1 ; i<num_proc ; i++)
{
    MPI_Recv(&sumREC , 1 , MPI_INT , i , 0 ,
MPI_COMM_WORLD , &status);

    sum = partial_sum + sumREC ;
}

clock_t t2 = clock();

cout<<"Sum = "<<sum<<"\n" ;
cout<<"\nTime elapsed: "<<(double)t2 - t1<<" ms";
}
else // SLAVE
{
    int data[50000000] ;

    MPI_Bcast(data , 5000000 , MPI_INT , 0 ,
MPI_COMM_WORLD);

    int partial_sum ;

    for(int i=partition_size ; i<5000000 ; i++)
        partial_sum = partial_sum + data[i] ;

    MPI_Send(&partial_sum , 1 , MPI_INT , my_rank , 0 ,
MPI_COMM_WORLD);
}
}

```

VI. INSERTION SORT ALGORITHM

Insertion sort is a simple sorting algorithm, it is a comparison sort in which the sorted array is built one entry at a time. In abstract terms, every iteration removes an element from the input data, inserting it at the correct position in the already sorted list, until no elements are left in the input [10].

In the proposed parallel algorithm, the master node will send the 1st input to slave node P, P will then check if the received number is smaller than a max value, if yes, it will send it to Pi+1, otherwise; it will send the max to Pi+1 and assign max a new value that is the number received. The algorithm is repeated until the whole list is sorted

A. Implementation

The proposed algorithm is implemented under MS Visual C++ 6.0. The message passing interface used is the proprietary MPI 2.0 standard DeinoMPI. As a testing platform, two computers connected by a 100Mbps Ethernet have been used with Intel Core Dual Core 1.66Ghz CPU and 512MB of DDR2 RAM. Table 6 delineates the results obtained

Table 6: Parallel Insertion Sort Testing Results

Number to sort	500
Sequential execution time	2s 203ms
Parallel execution time	1s 102ms
Speedup factor	$t_s / t_p = 2203/1102 = 1.99$

B. Source Code

```

void main(int argc, char* argv[])
{
    int my_rank; // Holds my rank: 0 for master and other
                // numbers for slaves
    int num_proc; // Holds the number of processors
                // available

    MPI_Status status;

    MPI_Init(&argc, &argv);

    MPI_Comm_rank(MPI_COMM_WORLD, &my_rank);

    MPI_Comm_size(MPI_COMM_WORLD, &num_proc);

    int max=-1 ;

    if (my_rank == 0) // MASTER
    {
        int data[500] = ; // List to sort

        for(int j=0 ; j<500 ; j++)
            data[j] = (int)rand() ;

        clock_t t1 = clock();

        for(int i=0 ; i<500 ; i++)
        {
            MPI_Send(&data[i] , 1 , MPI_INT , my_rank+1 , 0);
        }

        clock_t t2 = clock();

        cout<<"\nTime elapsed: "<<(double)t2 - t1<<" ms";
    }
    else // SLAVE
    {
        int number;

        MPI_Recv(&number , 1 , MPI_INT , my_rank-1 , 0 ,
&status);

        if(max== -1) // 1st time
            max=number ;
        else if(my_rank!=num_proc-1)
        {
            if(number<max)
                MPI_Send(&number , 1 , MPI_INT , my_rank+1 ,
0);
            else
            {
                // send to Pi+1

                MPI_Send(&max , 1 , MPI_INT , my_rank+1 , 0);
                max = number ;
            }
        }
    }
}
}

```

VII. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

This paper presented several computing algorithms that were originally designed for single processing. These algorithms are respectively the Mandelbrot set, the Bucket Sort, the Monte Carlo, the Grayscale Image Transformation, the Array Summation, and the Insertion Sort algorithm. All these algorithms were redesigned to execute in a parallel computing environment namely distributed message passing systems. They were implemented using C#.NET, the MPI.NET SDK, and the DeinoMPI API. Experiments showed that the proposed parallel algorithms have a substantial speed-up in execution time by multitude of factors.

As future work, the proposed algorithms are to be rewritten for shared memory architectures making the use of multi-threading, multi-processor, and multi-core systems.

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